

agro BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Coordination and Support Action

“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report

Responsible Partner: CREA

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N° 101000788.

"Let's meet!" Event Validation Report – Italy

Issued by: CREA
Issue date: 14/03/2023
Due date: 30/04/2023
Work Package Leader: MTU (Task Leader: Q-PLAN)

Start date of project: 01 January 2021

Duration: 36 months

Document History

Version	Date	Changes
1.0	09/03/2023	CREA first draft
2.0	21/03/2023	Final version

Dissemination Level

PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

Main authors	
Name	Organisation
Laura Gennaro, Andres Penalosa, Sibilla Berni Canani, Ilenia Manetti, Patrizia Borsotto, Francesca Giare	CREA

Quality reviewers	
Name	Organisation
George Malliopoulos, Eirini Efthymiadou	Q-PLAN

LEGAL NOTICE

The information and views set out in this report are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

© agroBRIDGES Consortium, 2022 - 2023

Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Table of Contents

1.	INTRODUCTION	5
2.	“LET’S MEET!” EVENT ORGANISATION DETAILS	6
2.1	Concept selection and definition of activities (programme)	6
2.2	Location, Venue/Space selection and arrangements	7
2.3	Personnel involved in the organisation of the event.....	9
2.4	Event material.....	10
2.5	Engagement of contributors and collaborators.....	12
2.6	Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation	12
3.	EVENT IMPLEMENTATION AND OUTCOMES	13
3.1	Event implementation	13
3.2	Event participation.....	18
4.	EVENT VALIDATION	19
4.1.1	<i>Validation of event concept by participants</i>	19
4.1.2	<i>Validation of “Let’s meet!” guidelines and templates by the organising partner</i>	20
4.1.3	<i>Limitations and barriers of the organising partner</i>	21
4.1.4	<i>Suggestions for improvement of the concept and guidelines</i>	21

List of figures

Figure 2: Kitchen and Multimedia room	8
Figure 3: Flyer, Programme and two mentimeter outcomes.....	11
Figure 4: presentations from CREA researchers.....	13

List of tables

Table 1: Event programme	6
Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event.....	10
Table 3: Event participation.....	18

1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of **CREA** for the organisation and validation of the **“Dai campi al suppli” (from fields to suppli) event in Rome, Italy on March 3rd, 2023**. This event is one of the four “Let’s meet!” event concepts designed in agroBRIDGES Task 3.4 for the local promotion of Short Food Supply Chains, locally produced food and involved market actors, namely (i) Producer Events, (ii) Culinary Events, (iii) Celebrate local heroes / SFSCs, and (iv) Open Days. The organisation, planning and implementation of the event was performed using the guidelines and templates designed by FBCD for each event concept to enable actors in the agri-food sector in replicating the events in their local agri-food ecosystems.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agroBRIDGES partner, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation, and implementation of the “Dai campi al suppli” event in Rome, Italy.
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the “Let’s meet!” guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool.

2. “Let’s meet!” event organisation details

2.1 Concept selection and definition of activities (programme)

For the Italian event, CREA (Council for Research in Agriculture and the Analysis of Agricultural Economics) decided to organize a culinary event in the form of a cooking show. So, on **3 March 2023**, CREA event took place, as part of the agroBRIDGES project, dedicated to Agricultural Technical Institute (ITA) Emilio Sereni’s students, at their facilities.

Thanks to the collaboration and availability of the ITA school headmaster, Prof. Patrizia Marini, the event was held in the *Locanda del Pellegrino* restaurant inside the school.

It allowed students to deepen the concept of short food supply chain and healthy and sustainable nutrition.

CREA intervened to present the project and to illustrate the opportunities and benefits that the short supply chain offers to producers and consumers.

The CO.R.AG.GIO Cooperative (Cooperativa Romana Agricoltura Giovani), a Roman multifunctional organic farming cooperative – already part of Italian MAP – presented its commitment to the promotion of short-chain products. After this short presentation part, **Giacomo Lepri** (President of the Cooperative and Chef) started preparing the recipe in the kitchen of the *Locanda del Pellegrino*, while students were watching in streaming from the adjacent conference room.

After the cooking show, all the participants were able to taste the prepared dish (suppli, a typical roman product but reinvented with local and short chain ingredients) and participated in the discussion giving their feedback, through the interactive presentation software (Mentimeter).

Due to the location capacity, only two student classes were able to participate but the event was recorded by the school technician to be shown to other students.

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Short description	Date & Time (local)	Location
Speech	Welcome of the school Headmaster	10:00 – 10:15	Restaurant <i>La locanda del Pellegrino</i> , in Emilio Sereni Agricultural Technical Institute (ITA) - Rome, Italy
Slides presentation	agroBRIDGES project and the role of Short Food Supply Chain (CREA); SFSC products in a healthy and sustainable diet (CREA); Cooperativa CO.R.AG.GIO	10:15 – 11:15	
Show cooking	The chef of cooperativa CO.R.AG.GIO at work.	11:15 – 12:00	

Title of activity	Short description	Date & Time (local)	Location
Tasting and feedback	All the participants tasted the short chain supplì giving their feedback through Mentimeter and the agroBRIDGES questionnaire	12:00 – 13:00	

2.2 Location, Venue/Space selection and arrangements

The choice of location, the Locanda del Pellegrino, made it possible to combine the presence of an optimal target, 2 class-groups of Agricultural's students and their teachers, with the facilities necessary for the event, i.e. an experimental kitchen available and a multimedia room connected to the kitchen.

The organization of the event took place in just over a month from the first contact with the school on 20 January 2023.

Once the location had been defined, it was possible to proceed with the search for the chef willing to prepare a dish based on local short-chain ingredients. Several MAP participants were consulted, and the CO.R.AG.GIO cooperative responded enthusiastically.

Figure 1: Kitchen and Multimedia room

2.3 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

For the organization and success of the event, 5 CREA researchers handled contacts and agreements with the Institute. CREA researchers supported by the administrative structure managed the bureaucratic aspects of selecting the cooperative (request for estimates).

CREA and Cooperativa CO.R.AG.GIO carried out on-site visit to the Institute to assess the spaces and the equipment. CREA researchers then took care of the preparation of the presentation slides and to facilitate discussion with the students and get them personally involved, virtual questionnaires were created using the [Mentimeter](#) platform. CREA researchers made their presentations, submitted the virtual questionnaires which they then commented on with the students. A CREA technician, with the support of the school technician, managed the transmission between the kitchen and the hall.

For the Sereni Technical Institute, the approval of the headmaster was required, who entrusted her deputy with the support of CREA in the organization.

From the Institute staff, two people were identified to supervise the activities in the kitchen and a technician to record the event.

On the part of the CO.R.AG.GIO cooperative, the event required the participation of 4 people: three of them dedicated only to the activities in the kitchen and the chef who alternated between cooking and explaining to the students and their teachers.

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
CREA researchers	5	Venue choice; organization and contacts; slide presentation; preparation of questionnaires on Mentimeter.	In-house	15 person days
CREA administrative staff	1	Tendering procedure	In-house	2 person days
CREA audio/video technician	1	Streaming organization and implementation	In-house	2 person days
ITA Sereni school headmaster and her Deputy	2	Consent to school facilities availability for free; Classes selection; welcome speech and attending the whole event	External	N/A
ITA Sereni kitchen staff	2	Kitchen supervision	External	N/A
ITA Sereni audio/video technician	1	Event recording	External	N/A
Cooperativa CO.R.AG.GIO staff	4	Speech; food procurement, preparation, and explanation	External	N/A

2.4 Event material

The materials produced following the “Let's meet!” guidelines were the programme, the poster and the presentation slides of the two topics discussed, the agroBRIDGES project and the inclusion of short-chain products in a healthy diet.

Furthermore, for a greater involvement of the students present, the Mentimeter tool has been used twice: first to ask the students which food they associate the concept of local and short-chain food with; then, during the tasting session, they were asked to identify an ingredient kept hidden (the white turnip) during the dish preparation, how much this recipe had surprised them and finally what ingredients they would choose to create an innovative suppli.

Quale ingrediente, non nominato, riconosci?

2.5 Engagement of contributors and collaborators

Once we decided to organise a culinary event and that our target audience was students, we identified an Agricultural Institute that was located in the Italian Beacon Region and had space for the event. We started contact with the school about 1.5 months before the event.

For the organization of the cooking show (culinary event), it was decided to involve the local MAP as much as possible since it includes HORECA stakeholders. Once the availability of the school restaurant was obtained, about a month before the event, requests for availability and cost estimates were sent to the 3 producers present in the MAP in the province of Rome who also provide catering services to the public. The CO.R.AG.GIO cooperative joined with great enthusiasm.

2.6 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

The 10th and 11th grade agricultural high school students were selected as the optimal target for this “Let’s meet!” event in agreement with the school.

No additional engagement actions were taken before the event since the maximum capacity of the event had been reached with students.

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

The Cooperativa CO.R.AG.GIO started its activities in the kitchen at 8.30 am. The CREA technician, in cooperation with the school technician, prepared the room for activities at 9.00 a.m.

At 10 a.m., work began. Before starting the speeches, CREA asked the students/teachers the following question: “Write down the name of three foods that come to mind when you think of short food supply chain or local products”. CREA presented the agroBridges project: slides were used, and the video realized as part of the project was shown: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HASukWBPdW>. The next presentation dealt with the definition of short supply chain and Italian regulations. The following intervention focused on short supply chain products in a healthy and sustainable diet. A small debate was then held with the students using the answers of the Mentimeter. Then the Cooperativa CO.R.AG.GIO presented itself by sharing with the students/teachers its experience as a possible employment outlet.

Figure 3: presentations from CREA researchers

Let's meet!: Dai campi al suppi

4

il CREA (Consiglio per la Ricerca in Agricoltura e l'Analisi dell'Economia Agraria) organizza un **cooking show** nell'ambito del progetto «**agroBRIDGES**» per gli studenti dell'I.T.A. **Emilio Sereni**, a Roma.

Sarà l'occasione per far conoscere il valore dei prodotti da **filiera corta** ai più giovani e per incentivare un'**alimentazione sana e sostenibile**.

Il **CREA** interverrà per presentare il progetto e per illustrare le opportunità e benefici che la filiera corta offre ai produttori e ai consumatori.

La **Cooperativa Coraggio** – realtà romana dedita alla produzione agroalimentare biologica – presenterà il proprio impegno nella promozione di prodotti di filiera corta cucinando per gli studenti.

Gli **studenti** assisteranno al **cooking show**, potranno degustare il piatto preparato e dare il loro feedback.

IL PROGETTO È FINANZIATO DAL PROGRAMMA EUROPEO DI RICERCA E INNOVAZIONE HORIZON 2020 CON ACCORDO DI SOVVENZIONE N° 101000788.

www.agrobridges.eu

Let's meet
03/03/2023

AGROBRIDGES – BUILDING BRIDGES BETWEEN PRODUCERS AND CONSUMERS

Prodotti di filiera corta in un'alimentazione
sana e sostenibile

Andrés Peñalosa, Laura Gennaro

THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT N° 101000788.

10

RIASSUNTO

Take-home messages

- ◆ DIETA SANA: piuttosto che un insieme qualsiasi di "prodotti sani", è il corretto equilibrio e la giusta combinazione di alimenti e dei diversi gruppi alimentari.
- ◆ CONOSCERE I PRODOTTI A FILIERA CORTA E LOCALI e inserirli nella nostra dieta, seguendo le Linee Guida per una Sana Alimentazione
- ◆ L'INFORMAZIONE, L'EDUCAZIONE E LA SENSIBILIZZAZIONE sono cruciali per poter fare le scelte e non cadere nelle trappole del marketing e i claims non basati sull'evidenza.
- ◆ Fondamentale la ricerca

THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT N° 101000788.

agr
BRIDGES

After a short break, the cooking show began.

The chief of the Cooperativa CO.R.AG.GIO explained the ingredients he would use - their origin - while keeping one of them hidden. The preparation of the Suppli and its cooking was then shown. Then the Suppli was tasted by the students/teachers.

Three questions were then administered through the mentimeter tool:

1 – “What is the secret ingredient?”

2 – “How much this dish has surprised you?”

3 - “What ingredients would you choose for make an innovative suppli?”

A small debate was then held with the students using the answers of the mentimeter.

Finally, we asked students/teachers to fill in the validation questionnaire prepared within the agroBRIDGES project.

Figure 3: Short chain Suppli and mentimeter screenshot with students' answers about foods from short chain

4. Event Validation

4.1.1 Validation of event concept by participants

The total respondents to the questionnaire were 56.

Question	Yes	No	Not sure	-	-	-
Were you familiar with the concept of Short Supply Chain before this event?	24	24	8			
Question	Very useful	useful	neutral	Not very useful	No useful at all	-
How helpful was the event in learning more about local products and on how treat them at best?	25	22	6	2	1	
Question	Very useful	useful	neutral	Not very useful	No useful at all	-
How helpful was the event in learning more about examples of local businesses (producers and restaurateurs), their work, and their commitment to local food production?	24	26	5	0	1	
Question	Very useful	useful	neutral	Not very useful	No useful at all	-
How useful were the activities organized in the event in helping people understand the value of local food, local recipes and their various benefits to health, the environment and society?	24	24	8	0	0	

Question	Yes, very precise	Yes, but I would have liked to know more	Yes, but I think I'll have to inform on my own a bit more	No, not enough	Not at all	-
Have you received enough information about the productive and HORECA activity you have encountered?	38	14	4	0	0	

Question	Monthly or more	3-4 times per year	Twice per year	1 time per year	never	Prefer not to answer
Would you like to see a similar event organized, perhaps in the area where you live? How often?	22	18	8	2	1	5

4.1.2 Validation of “Let’s meet!” guidelines and templates by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event concepts relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organization?

The event concepts were relevant to our organization. We used the templates provided by the tool to share the objectives of the event and the programme with our audience and the material was useful to share the activities also in our social media channels.

Question #2: Would you organise the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments?

We organized a show cooking involving students and professors at an Italian agricultural school (a culinary event in the let’s meet tool). It was considered a very useful event not only to introduce students to a local production reality, discovering products and services offered, but also to introduce them to the concepts of short supply chain and healthy and sustainable diet. Surely such an event in other schools would be successful if organized several times a year involving different realities. Materials offered by the tool are adequate and easily adaptable to the context and audience.

Question #3: Did you find the guidelines and templates sufficient for your event organization needs?

Yes, we did. Templates and guidelines were sufficient and adaptable to our event.

Question #4: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines accurate enough to plan effectively?

Yes, we think the guidelines are enough accurate to plan a culinary event effectively.

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

Yes, we did. In fact, we used templates adapting the information (also the final questionnaire) to our needs.

4.1.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

Having involved young students and being high in numbers, we had to administer the questionnaire in a paper-based manner at the end of the event to prevent feedback from being lost. Certainly, this then required additional work to digitally report the results obtained and analyse them.

4.1.4 Suggestions for improvement of the concept and guidelines

Question #6: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

Yes, the guideline offers flexible materials for adapting the material to our event.

All the stakeholders (the Agricultural Institute, the Cooperative and CREA itself) have found this event format very efficient, fruitful, interesting, and amusing. Surely to be replicated with other partners in other locations.